

AWARENESS OF NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY (2020) AMONG SCHOOL TEACHERS

Dr. Pravin Kale,

Assistant Professor,

PVDT College of Education for Women,

Mumbai-20

Abstract:

National Education Policy 2020 is one of the important landmark in the field of education. Reconstruction of education structure with development of 21st century skills, productivity of education, experiential learning, multilingual approach, importance to local elements in education holistic approach, development of critical and analytical thinking are important pillars of NEP. As far as evaluation is concerned continuous formative assessment of learning, assessment for learning is proposed. From the last three years we are discussing NEP 2020 but it is also a reality that the school teachers who are an important part of this policy are not completely aware about this policy, recommendations and proposed changes. This study is a small effort to understand the awareness of NEP among school teachers of Mumbai, Mumbai Suburban and Thane District of Maharashtra state.

Introduction:

The committee under the former Cabinet Secretary Shri. T.S.R. Subramanian was formed in January 2015 and started the consultation process for the New Education Policy. The panel of eminent scholars from various sectors was formed to prepare a draft of NEP. Krishnaswamy Kasturirangan from ISRO was the chief of this committee. After a number of public consultations, the committee submitted the draft of NEP to MHRD.

The National Education Policy of India 2020 (NEP 2020), which was approved by the Union Cabinet of India on 29 July 2020, outlines the vision of a new education system of India. The new policy replaces the previous National Policy on Education, 1986. The policy is a comprehensive framework for elementary education to higher education as well as vocational training in both rural and urban India. The policy aims to transform India's education system by 2040.

Various structural changes are proposed in NEP 2020 e.g., school curriculum and pedagogy are introduced with the new 5+3+3+4 design. The Foundational Stage will consist of five years of flexible, multilevel, play/activity-based learning and the curriculum and pedagogy of ECCE as mentioned. The policy aimed at developing 21st century skills among learners. Rote learning replaced by experiential learning. The emphasis of the NEP is on conceptual understanding rather than rote learning and learning-for-exams. Creativity, critical thinking, analytical thinking, use of machine learning, artificial intelligence, use of technology are important characteristics of this policy. Competency based education will be helpful to

maximize output of education. Not only scholastic achievement but inculcation of values is given immense importance. The policy also ensures continued formative assessment of learning. There are many more steps taken to ensure quality education to the masses. The policy proposed a four year integrated teacher training course to prepare quality teachers, school accreditation framework, teacher upgradation and professional development, TET for teacher recruitment and so on. Importance is given to classical languages with a multilingual approach. Digital Infrastructure for Knowledge Sharing are remarkable proposed changes in NEP. Children with special needs are also taken care of while planning this NEP 2020. Special Educational Zones will be there for educationally-disadvantaged. NEP is comprehensive education from ECCE to Higher education is taken care of. In higher education HEIs are motivated to go for autonomy for more academic flexibility. Provisions for strengthening Open and Distance Learning are also given, furthermore it is also suggested that the online education system also should be used in the ODL system. The various initiatives mentioned above will also help in having larger numbers of international students studying in India, and provide greater mobility to students in India who may wish to visit, study at, transfer credits to, or carry out research at institutions abroad, and vice versa. The Choice Based Credit System (CBCS) is also one of the important provisions in higher education. Surely, with the implementation of NEP 2020 we will see a changed picture of education at all levels and the impact will reflect in society.

Importance of Study: The NEP 2020 too exhorts, ‘Teachers truly shape the future of our children – and, therefore, the future of our nation’ thereby implying that teachers play the most important role in nation-building by creating high quality human resources in their classrooms. *Recognising the ‘power of teacher’* NEP 2020 has put in place systemic reforms that would help ‘teaching’ emerge as an attractive profession of choice for bright and talented young minds. It proposes several reforms to empower teachers and *‘restore the high respect and status’* to this profession hoping that it would eventually attract the best minds and talent to choose teaching as their profession. The policy will help to bring our dream of transforming India’s Education System into reality. There are a lot of expectations from teachers at all levels of education because the responsibility of implementation of this policy effectively is on the shoulders of teachers. There are so many provisions made in NEP 2020 for the betterment of teachers, their professional development, job satisfaction, motivation. It is very important that teachers at all levels of education should understand the recommendations, policy framework, and provisions made in NEP 2020 for effective implementation. So, it is necessary to study whether the proposed policy is reached up to teachers or not?. Still we have some time during which we can organize training programs for the teachers. On the basis of the result analysis of the survey, teacher training colleges and government organizations can organize NEP awareness programs for the teachers in the near future.

Objectives of the study:

For the present study the researcher had formulated the following objectives.

- 1) To study the awareness of NEP among school teachers.

- 2) To compare awareness of NEP 2020 among teachers of Government schools and Private schools.
- 3) To study the training/ orientation needs of school teachers regarding NEP 2020.

Methodology and Sample of the study:

For the present study the researcher has selected a survey method. The data is collected through Google Forms. The Google Form was circulated through WhatsApp, Gmail and other social networking sites. For the present study teachers teaching at primary, secondary and higher secondary sections are considered. Only the teachers from Mumbai, Mumbai Suburban and Thane district are included in the present study. The researcher has received responses of 412 teachers.

Tool of the data Collection: The researcher has developed a questionnaire and used Google Form for the circulation of the questionnaire. There were 30 items in the questionnaire which were related to the study of awareness of NEP among school teachers. In the questionnaire 22 items were related to various recommendations and changes proposed in NEP 2020. Rest of the 8 questions were related to understanding the training needs of the teachers and other aspects. In the 22 items if the teachers were not knowing the correct answer they were given freedom to skip a particular question.

Statistical Techniques Used: For the analysis of the data a simple statistical tool i.e., percentage is used.

Analysis of the Data: On the basis of responses received following facts are revealed.

- 1) As far as the training program is concerned, only 35% teachers have attended training/ orientation programs related to NEP.
- 2) 65% teachers have not attended any type of training program, most of the teachers have received basic information related to NPE through social media, discussion with colleagues, and through newspapers.
- 3) These training programs/ awareness programs/ orientations were organized by teacher training Colleges, Private organizations and Government bodies (DIET, SCERT, Municipal Corporation and Zilla Parishad)
- 4) 61% teachers have partial understanding about recommendations given in NPE whereas 23% teachers have little understanding, 10% teachers are unaware about various recommendations of NPE. Only 6% teachers have complete understanding about NPE 2020.
- 5) 100% teachers conveyed that they need orientation and training programs to understand recommendations and suggested policy framework given in NPE 2020.
- 6) 81% Teachers prefer online training/ orientation programs regarding NEP 2020.
- 7) As far as teachers working in Private schools, Private aided schools and Govt. Schools not very much difference in understanding of NPE is found. All need more inputs and training programs to understand NPE.
- 8) Only 6% teachers know important recommendations and key features of NPE 2020.

Recommendations on the basis of above findings:

On the basis of data analysis following recommendations can be given.

- 1) Comprehensive orientation sessions should be organized for the school teachers regarding NEP 2020.
- 2) There should be more TV programs regarding NEP.
- 3) Government and private organizations should prepare small booklets and provide them to teachers.
- 4) Teachers should be motivated to participate in seminars, workshops regarding NEP2020.

Conclusion:

Teachers were going to play a major role in implementation of NEP at grassroot level, they must have complete understanding of educational framework, policies, recommendation etc. When teachers understand NEP 2020 then definitely there will be effective implementation from them. *'The secret of success is to be ready when your opportunity comes!'* For Indian teachers' time has come to seize the opportunity and become makers of India's destiny.

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